

Network Digital Twinning Solutions to Increase the Security of Multi-Domain Optical Transport Networks

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Autonomous networking relies on technologies such as Network Digital Twins (NDT), which might apply machine learning (ML) techniques to reduce the computational complexity of analytical models. Centralized NDTs are typically fed with telemetry collected from the data plane to implement observe-analyze-act control loops for intelligent network diagnosis and decision-making. NDT can estimate the performance of optical connections, which has multiple operational applications, from provisioning to failure management. However, the resulting ML pipelines require special attention not only in terms of efficiency and scalability, but also in terms of security since the attack surface increases in distributed systems. In consequence, autonomous operation requires from security mechanisms. This fact is more evident in the case of multi-domain networks. Specifically, because envisioned end-to-end (e2e) 6G networks expand through multiple administrative and technological domains, security and privacy issues need to be considered on the autonomous multi-domain optical layer operation. In this paper, we concentrate on multi-domain optical transport networks operated autonomously with the support of ML-based NDTs modelling the optical layer. We propose NDT-based solutions to detect combined attacks of data tampering and model evasion that compromise the security of the optical network. To that end, e2e multi-domain models are required, which can be created as a concatenation of intra-domain NDT models modeling each domain. We aim to provide solutions to preserve the privacy of the domains. Simulation results demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed solutions in terms of relevant security-related metrics, such as combined attack detection accuracy and privacy-preserving scoring.

1. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous networking (AN) is the fundamental pillar towards seamless, zero-touch operation of next-generation networks. In this regard, the TM Forum provides operators with strategic plans to guide their journey towards AN by the adoption of frameworks that allow the implementation and evaluation of progressive AN Levels (ANL) [1]. The roadmap of major network operators envisions the achievement of fully autonomous systems (ANL5) across multiple network technologies (including optical) and domains by 2030 [2]. Thanks to the broad use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML), intelligent network control and management systems are expected to incorporate native intelligence with essential capabilities, such as self-learning, self-detection, and self-healing towards the successful achievement of ANL5 [3]. Among different use cases of ML for network automation, the estimation of the Quality of Transmission (QoT) of optical connections (*lightpath*) has received large research interest [4].

A key system involved in the autonomous operation of optical networks is the network digital twin (NDT). According to IETF definition, an NDT is a virtual representation of the real network used to analyze, diagnose, emulate, and then control the real-network based on data, models, and interfaces [5]. NDTs might use complex analytical models and include detailed information of the network to achieve accurate results. In addition, ML techniques are applied to reduce the computational complexity of specific analytical models so as to speed up the computing process.

Typically, NDTs are independent *centralized* entities that provide inputs to Software Defined Networking (SDN) systems in charge of network control and management. Hence, tightly integrated NDT-based intelligence and existing SDN-controllers becomes a promising option towards ANL5, although it is not exempt of challenges and open issues [6]. In addition, the heterogeneity of optical systems and devices, where proprietary and disaggregated systems might co-exist, leads to complex scenarios to model [7].

NDTs need to be continuously fed with telemetry collected from the data plane, so a key system connecting for the control

plane to get feedback from the data plane is the telemetry system [8]. The telemetry system includes distributed telemetry data processing [9], typically based on ML techniques including supervised feature extraction and compression based on auto-encoder (AE), and data delivery, and together with centralized ML-based intelligence define a set of ML pipelines [10], which are essential for autonomous network operation [11].

An example of NDT for the optical layer is the OCATA optical time domain NDT [12-13], an accurate and efficient tool with multiple autonomous operation -related applications [14]. OCATA NDT relies on Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) for optical constellations (OC) feature extraction and deep neural networks (DNN) to model the expected effects of individual optical devices and fibers on signal propagation in the optical time domain. Such effects impact the shape of OCs. Thus, by concatenating DNNs for the elements in the route of a lightpath, expected characteristics and performance can be accurately computed, including: transmission distance from transmitter (Tx) to receiver (Rx) [12], and QoT estimation, e.g., the pre-forward error correction (pre-FEC) bit error rate (BER) [13]. Such metrics obtained from the NDT are relevant, not only during provisioning and operation of lightpaths, i.e., for fast and accurate QoT-aware lightpath operation, but also for the security of the optical layer as a whole, including both optical transmission and autonomous operation.

In the last years, the use of ML for the secure operation of optical networks has been mainly focused on optical layer attack management [15], while leaving the study of the security related to the ML models enabling AN operation poorly investigated. Thus, although ML pipelines themselves can be protected from optical layer attacks, their distributed nature increases the potential attack surface, which poses additional challenges to increase robustness and security of intelligent network operation systems against multiple threats. In fact, some network operators are still reluctant to integrate AN operation in their legacy infrastructure due to, among others, security-related issues such as data protection, data sovereignty, and AI robustness and trustworthiness [2]. In particular, recent contributions to develop confidentiality-preserving ML pipelines, including optical telemetry collection and processing [16], show the interest on solutions providing robust and trustworthy AN operation.

Note that the added complexity brought by disaggregation at the optical layer can increase vulnerabilities that can be exploited by attackers. For instance, in case of a *Man-in-the-Middle* (MitM) attack [17], the affected lightpath is intercepted by the attacker (Mallory) at an intermediate site between the Tx (Alice) and the Rx (Bob), with the objective of *tampering* transmitted data. To do so, Mallory needs a pair of optical transceivers to receive the optical signal from Alice, alter the received data, and generate a new optical signal that is sent to Bob. The use of NDTs allows enhancing the security of the optical layer. In this particular example, the optical signal received by Bob has physical properties related to the actual transmission distance. Hence, the accurate estimation of expected lightpath properties and its comparison against actual collected measurements allows a fast and accurate MitM attack detection, which eventually triggers countermeasures to react against such incident.

The use of NDTs brings additional security concerns. An inherent characteristic of NDTs is their potential risk to specific AI/ML threats that can affect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CI&A) of their models and algorithms [18]. One of the most relevant AI-specific threats is called *model evasion*, where adversaries alter input data of ML models with the aim to produce a misleading output and eventually leading to wrong decision making [19]. An example of data evasion in OC samples was presented in our previous work in [20], where OC patterns were modified to maliciously alter the behavior of the ML model for lightpath distance estimation. When this evasion attack is combined with the data tampering attack, the latter becomes very difficult to detect.

The complexity increases when multiple network domains need to be considered, since domain NDTs need to collaborate to create end-to-end (e2e) models involving several domains. For instance, at the optical layer, those domains supporting an e2e lightpath can share models trained for the intra-domain network to create an e2e model [21], thus extending the scope of ML pipelines (and its complexity) beyond the limits of a single domain. Note that this is precisely the scenario of the envisioned 6G networking, with services spanning multiple domains and requiring stringent e2e performance. Therefore, security and privacy issues require special attention [22], so it is paramount to devise novel architectures, protocols, and procedures for the secure operation of multi-domain networks. For instance, authors in [23] presented a methodology for QoT estimation in multi-domain networks assuming that the internals of some domains are hidden for privacy-preserving purposes. In addition, authors in [24] proposed distributed learning methods for QoT estimation while obviating the need for confidential intra-domain data.

In this work, we rely on the OCATA NDT, which supports a wide range of AN operation applications including QoT estimation and attack management in multi-domain optical networks. Note that intra-domain model concatenation enables fast e2e lightpath model availability, in contrast to distributed learning approaches. However, OCATA NDT models incorporate details of the intra-domain network, e.g., the number of hops, the length of optical links, the configuration of optical devices, etc. Therefore, distributing such models to other domains have many security and privacy concerns since such information could be used to craft specific attacks in case of eavesdropping. In consequence, any information of the internals of the domain must be removed before intra-domain models leave the security perimeter of the domain. A possible approach is to train a black-box domain model that mimic the performance of the combination of component models. In addition to the time needed for training, this approach would require generating the response of the concatenated model in the expected working region of the data space to obtain a synthetic training dataset from which the black-box model can be trained (see [25]). Another approach to create exportable intra-domain

models is the privacy-preserving model sharing methodology proposed in our previous paper in [26].

This paper extends [26] and focuses on providing solutions to increase the security and privacy of autonomous operation of multi-domain optical network based on the OCATA NDT. A novel approach is proposed for guaranteeing privacy and security, where domain NDTs are extended with capabilities to support model exchange with other domains. E2e models are used as part of a procedure to detect evasion attacks applied to OC samples in sophisticated MitM attacks.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 sketches the reference multi-domain architecture and highlights the major security and privacy related components and features that need to be considered for robust and reliable multi-domain optical network operation based on OCATA NDT functionalities and capabilities. Section 3 presents the privacy preserving model sharing methodology. This section extends [26] with a detailed workflow of the proposed methodology for the use case of e2e multi-domain lightpath provisioning, as well as provide new algorithms to maximize privacy of exportable models and quantify its degree of privacy. Section 4 presents an attack use case for the proposed multi-domain scenario, where an adversary performs MitM attack that combines data tampering and model evasion to evade attack detection in OCATA NDT. This MitM attack methodology is adapted from [20], where the threat was presented for single domain optical networks. Then, a novel procedure to detect model evasion is presented in order to successfully detect such combined attack. Section 5 presents numerical evaluation results in a simulation-based environment of the methods presented in Sections 3 and 4. Based on openly available OC samples [27], performance evaluation concentrates on showing the enhanced privacy of exportable models, as well on the accuracy to detect combined MitM attacks with data tampering and model evasion. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and shows an overall view of the threats, vulnerabilities, and countermeasures considered in this paper.

2. SECURE MULTI-DOMAIN NETWORK OPERATION

Figure 1a illustrates the reference multi-domain network architecture by means of an example consisting of three domains (labeled $D1$, $D2$, and $D3$). For the sake of illustrative purposes, an e2e connection between sites A and Z (in orange color in Figure 1a) is depicted, representing either: *i*) a new multi-domain connectivity request; or *ii*) an already established multi-domain lightpath. On top of the architecture, the *orchestrator* is in charge of managing the process of provisioning e2e connections as well as supervising and guaranteeing the committed QoT of established multi-domain lightpaths.

Without loss of generality, we assume that the main control plane elements needed for autonomous operation of a given domain are hosted and running in one centralized domain site (hereafter, referred as *CP site*). These control plane elements are: *i*) the *SDN controller* in charge of providing intra-domain connectivity, as well as other procedures and policies related with QoT assurance; *ii*) the *telemetry manager*, that receives telemetry from distributed *telemetry agents* and feeds other components with the current status of the underlying system; and *iii*) the *OCATA NDT* that models the domain optical layer in order to perform QoT estimation and analysis during both provisioning and operation phases. Recall that this hierarchical domain control architecture with pervasive telemetry support has been recently proposed and successfully evaluated as key enabler of domain autonomous operation [8]. Moreover, the architecture in Figure 1 is fully aligned with the experimental demonstration [28]. Assuming the aforementioned control and management architecture, let us now focus on security and privacy aspects concerning multi-domain optical connections (Figure 1 b). At provisioning time and with the aim to evaluate the expected QoT of a multi-domain connectivity request, an e2e model Φ needs to be built. Assuming that the domain CP site where OCATA NDT component runs is a secure environment with high protection against CI&A threats and incidents, we can assume that intra-domain models η are inside a secure perimeter. However, the target Φ model consists in the concatenation of intra-domain models that need to be shared and gathered in a single site for its usage. Hence, intra-domain models of source and intermediate domains must be shared in a secure and private way to the destination site where the e2e Φ lightpath model is composed and used for e2e QoT analysis purposes.

Figure 1. Reference multi-domain architecture (a); proposed scheme (b)

The aforementioned model sharing requires from implementing two key security measures. On the one hand, *privacy preserving domain model synthesis* is performed inside the domain secure perimeter in order to obtain exportable models φ that hide any sensitive information of the internals of the domain. On the other hand, *secure inter-domain model sharing* must be implemented by some means of secure connectivity. In this regard, we rely on the combined use of Virtual eXtensible Local-Area Network (VXLAN) as tunneling/encapsulation protocol and IP security (IPsec) for adding encryption and authentication to IP packets, as efficient and secure way for model exchange between remote agents and systems [11, 29].

Once the exportable models have been securely received at destination domain, the *e2e model composition* can be securely performed. A good practice when doing this composition is to keep the privacy preservation that domain models have, so the e2e model inherits that privacy and becomes less vulnerable to potential model disclosure attacks in case that CP site security seal is compromised. The e2e model is used by the ML-based lightpath analysis module that performs several actions. At provisioning time, it is in charge of estimating the expected QoT of the multi-domain request, which is a metric required by the orchestrator to eventually decide whether the request can be established or not.

Let us now assume that the e2e connection is established and the e2e model is available at the OCATA NDT of the destination site. Since the model reproduces the expected behavior of the optical connection, this expectation can be compared with the actual performance obtained by the telemetry system in order to detect mismatches and reveal potential attacks. Thus, telemetry data collected from the Rx at the agent of the destination node needs to be securely processed before sending to the manager at the CP site. Besides taking advantage of the aforementioned combination of VXLAN + IPsec for *secure intra-domain data sharing*, additional privacy amplification mechanisms need to be implemented. In this regard, the combination of techniques such as data aggregation, summarization and compression techniques [8] not only reduce the volume of telemetry data to be shared, but also increase the privacy of the ML pipeline, which reduces the chance of effective data disclosure attacks.

In the next sections, we focus on the description, methodology and algorithms related to privacy preserving model synthesis and composition during provisioning time (Section 3), and related to AI-based lightpath analysis for the detection of tampering and poisoning incidents performed by a MitM attack (Section 4).

3. PRIVACY PRESERVING MODEL SHARING

In this section we present the main components for privacy preserving model sharing in multi-domain networks. First, we present the detailed architecture of OCATA NDT building blocks and models running in each domain CP site, including e2e and segment models. Then, the main workflow used during lightpath provisioning phase is detailed. Note that during provisioning phase, models are generated and shared among domains and therefore, privacy must be ensured. Among different processes involved in the workflow, exportable model synthesis process is key for guaranteeing privacy. A section is devoted to explain the algorithms and assumptions of this procedure. Finally, a methodology to check and guarantee the enhanced privacy of the models shared among domains is presented. Two different scores are formally introduced, which will be used for privacy evaluation.

A. Architecture and workflow

Figure 2a and Figure 2b sketches the internals of OCATA NDT in source/intermediate domains and destination domain, respectively, of a multi-domain lightpath. In both cases, the DT processes the intra-domain route segment p of the lightpath received from the local SDN controller (1 in Fig. 1) and builds a disaggregated model η that characterizes the segment by concatenating trained component models from the local model DB (including models for ROADMs and links). Each component is modelled as a feed-forward DNN that receives as input the set of features F , that characterize IQ constellation points as bivariate Gaussian distributions with its mean position (μ_I and μ_Q), its variance (σ_I and σ_Q), and covariance (σ_{IQ}), i.e., five features per constellation point. The model propagates forward the features emulating the physical behavior of the component, so that it outputs the set of modified features after component propagation (see [12] for additional details of the models). As a consequence of this, the disaggregated segment model η can be seen as a large sequence of DNN layers, where components are easy to distinguish due to the recognizable shape and structure of input/output component layers.

As introduced in Section 2, source and intermediate domains of the lightpath (Figure 2a) might share intra-domain models with the destination with enhanced and guaranteed privacy preservation. Therefore, intra-domain model synthesis is carried out in the domains sharing their models to generate exportable segment models φ from the disaggregated ones. Exportable models might eliminate the clear separation of the different components by properly fusing them in an indistinguishable segment model that hides the internals of the route such as number of hops and characteristics (length) of fiber links. In addition, in the destination domain OCATA NDT (Figure 2b), the e2e model is generated by concatenating the received segments models as well as the final segment of the own destination domain. As an additional privacy preserving countermeasure, the same procedure applied to create exportable segment models is applied to the e2e model.

Figure 2. Architecture at source and intermediate domains (a) and destination domain (b); workflow during e2e lightpath provisioning (c)

Figure 3. Example of messages exchanged during e2e lightpath provisioning workflow

Figure 2c illustrates the workflow that is executed upon the reception of a new e2e connectivity request. In addition, in Figure 3 shows the contents of some message examples. Note that this request needs from the evaluation of the expected QoT to decide whether the request can be accepted or not. Therefore, the composition of the e2e model is necessary for such QoT evaluation.

First of all, the orchestrator computes a candidate inter-domain route R (i.e., the sequence of domains to traverse from source to destination) and assigns a unique identified rid to it (labelled as 1 in Figure 2c). After that, the computation of the intra-domain routes of each traversed domain is requested to the domain SDN controllers. In all the domains, the segment route p is computed and stored (2), and the model is generated in OCATA NDT. Note that for source/intermediate domains, the generated model includes exportable model synthesis (3), whereas only disaggregated model is generated at the destination domain (4). An example of message (3) is shown in Figure 3; it contains the route identifier rid , the identifier of the domain, and the exportable DNN model. This model consists in a sequence of layers, each identified by a type and some characteristics such as the number

of units (neurons) and activation function. Moreover, the trained weights of each layer are included as a list of matrices, following the same order than that of the sequence of layers. After the process of each domain is terminated, the reply is sent back to the orchestrator (5). This reply will include the exportable model for source/intermediate domains. When the orchestrator receives the reply from all the domains in the e2e path, then it sorts the received exportable models in the correct order for the e2e path, and requests the destination domain to compose the e2e model from the list of ordered exportable models (6). An example of message (6) is shown in Figure 3; note that only models from source and intermediate domains are added in the body of the message (omitted in the figure). Then, the destination domain will generate model ϕ , store it, and send back the confirmation reply (7).

At this stage, the destination domain owns the e2e model ϕ required to e2e QoT evaluation. Thus, the orchestrator requests it to compute the relevant QoT metrics for provisioning decision making (8), e.g., expected BER computed from the propagated OC features [13]. The QoT metrics are computed and replied to the orchestrator (9), that will be in charge of making the final provisioning decision (accept/reject), comparing the expected metrics obtained with OCATA NDT with the requirements that the connection must guarantee (10). An example of QoT metrics message is also depicted in Figure 3, which includes: *i*) the bivariate Gaussian features that characterize the constellation points of the expected signal, *ii*) the expected e2e distance according to lightpath model, and *iii*) the expected pre-FEC BER computed from the expected features.

Considering that the request is eventually accepted, the request to setup the intra-domain connectivity using the computed intra-domain route is sent to each domain (11). The e2e connection is finally established once confirmation replies from all domains are received by the orchestrator (12). It is worth mentioning that the e2e model at the destination domain is still valid and can be afterwards used for other purposes such as continuous QoT assurance, as well as for detecting anomalies and/or attacks. Once the e2e lightpath is established, the accuracy of the e2e model can be evaluated. To that end, OC samples can be continuously collected and compared to the output of the e2e model. In the case that fine-tuning is needed, such OC samples can be used to adjust the model hyperparameters using the approach presented in [30]. Since data collection and fine-tuning remain in the security perimeter of destination domain, no data sharing between domains is required and therefore, privacy is preserved.

Note that e2e models might need to be updated during lightpath lifetime, e.g., due to: *i*) component model update because of device aging; *ii*) intra-domain segment rerouting; and *iii*) e2e lightpath rerouting. In the first two cases, the affected domain should trigger a notification to the orchestrator to start the workflow in Figure 2c to regenerate and update the exportable model, while in the last case, that workflow is started after by the orchestrator the lightpath rerouting.

B. Exportable model synthesis

This section details the procedure carried out by source and intermediate domains of an e2e lightpath to generate exportable intra-domain models ϕ from disaggregated models η . To this aim, two different sets of component models are available in the local model DB within the OCATA NDT (see Figure 2): First, the *symmetric non-linear biased* (SNLB) set contains highly accurate DNNs with: *i*) equal number of neurons per layer; and *ii*) non-linear activation functions (e.g., hyperbolic tangent, tanh) and non-zero bias for every hidden and output neuron. This set is used to build η , which is expected to provide the highest fidelity to model the intra-domain lightpath segment. Second, the *asymmetric linear un-biased* (ALUB) set contains component models where: *i*) each layer has a different number of neurons; and *ii*) the activation function of the first hidden layer and output layer is linear and the bias of the first hidden layer and output layer is zero. This set is used to generate an alternative disaggregated model η' . Although η is more accurate than η' , the latter exhibits good properties for security that allow easily hiding the concatenation of consecutive components by merging layers, thus obtaining a layered intra-domain model whose components cannot be isolated.

The overall procedure is detailed in Algorithm I, which receives the disaggregated intra-domain model η , models set ALUB, and a threshold *trunc* for truncating non-significant model coefficients. Without loss of generality, we assume that every single component model in η has k alternative models in ALUB, each of them with different number and configuration of hidden layers. After initializing model η' (line 1 in Algorithm I), a model for each component in η is selected from the ALUB set and added to η' (lines 2-3).

Algorithm II details the procedure of that model selection, which aims at finding the model compatible with the type of component that maximizes the diversity (*div*) with respect to the component models already added to η' . Thus, after initializing *div* to 0, all the models in ALUB that match with the type of the target component are retrieved and individually evaluated in terms of diversity (lines 1-2 in Algorithm II). The evaluation of a given model m_1 consists in computing the minimum diversity with respect to all the models m_2 in η' (lines 3-10). Diversity is computed in terms of the Euclidean distance (*dist*) in the multi-dimensional space of model hyperparameters defined in vector Z , i.e., a vector of size n_{max} containing the number of neurons at each layer, where n_{max} is the maximum number of layers in a model. The position in the vector indicates the position of the layer from input to output. For those models with a number of layers $n < n_{max}$, 0 is set for positions $[n+1, n_{max}]$. Then, the procedure returns the model m^* that maximizes the minimum diversity with respect to the models in η' (lines 11-14).

Algorithm I. Exportable model synthesis procedure

IN: $\eta, \text{ALUB}, \text{trunc}$	OUT: $\varphi, s1, s2$
1: $\eta' \leftarrow \emptyset$	
2: for i in $1.. p $ do	
3: $\eta' \leftarrow \eta' \cup \text{selectModel}(\text{ALUB}, \eta[i].\text{type}, \eta')$	
4: $\varphi \leftarrow \text{mergeComponents}(\eta')$ (eq. (1) and Figure 4)	
5: $\varphi \leftarrow \text{shuffleHiddenNeurons}(\varphi)$	
6: $\varphi \leftarrow \text{truncateCoeffs}(\varphi, \text{trunc})$	
7: return φ	

Algorithm II. selectModel procedure

IN: $\text{ALUB}, \text{type}, \eta'$	OUT: m^*
1: $\text{div} \leftarrow 0$	
2: for m_1 in $\text{filter}(\text{ALUB}, \text{type})$ do	
3: $\text{dist}' \leftarrow \text{inf}$	
4: $Z_1 \leftarrow \text{getProperties}(m_1)$	
5: for m_2 in η' do	
6: $Z_2 \leftarrow \text{getProperties}(m_2)$	
7: $\text{dist} \leftarrow \text{L2norm}(Z_1, Z_2)$	
8: if $\text{dist} < \text{dist}'$ then	
9: $m' \leftarrow m_2$	
10: $\text{dist}' \leftarrow \text{dist}$	
11: if $\text{div} < \text{dist}'$ then	
12: $m^* \leftarrow m'$	
13: $\text{div} \leftarrow \text{dist}'$	
14: return m^*	

Figure 4. DNN layer merging

Coming back to Algorithm I and after building model η' , a merging procedure between consecutive component models is applied (line 4). This procedure is sketched in Figure 4 for models u and v (each with n layers), where $u(i)$ denotes the i -th layer of model u . Thus, weights α (for connections between the last hidden layer and the output of model u) and β (for connections between the input layer and the first hidden layer of model v) can be linearly merged to obtain new weights γ using eq (1):

$$\gamma_{ij} = \sum_{k \in F} \alpha_{ik} \cdot \beta_{kj} \quad \forall i \in u(n-1), j \in v(2) \quad (1)$$

Although the exportable model φ is ready at this point, layer *obfuscation* makes more difficult getting lightpath details by model inspection. Thus, neurons are randomly shuffled within their layer and weights and biases are truncated to 0 if they are lower than trunc before returning the final model (lines 5-6).

Algorithm III. Score s1

IN: model (either η or φ)	OUT: $s1$
1: $n_{\max} \leftarrow \text{getNumberOfLayers}(\text{model})$	
2: $s1 \leftarrow \text{zeros}(n_{\max})$	
3: $F_{in} \leftarrow \text{generateRandomInputFeatures}()$	
4: $F_{out} \leftarrow \text{model.forward}(F_{in})$	
5: for i in $[2, n_{\max}-1]$ do	
6: if $\text{size}(\text{model}[i]) == \text{size}(\text{model}[n_{\max}])$ then	
7: $F_{aux} \leftarrow \text{model}[1..i].\text{forward}(F_{in})$	
8: $s1[i] \leftarrow 1/\text{MSE}(F_{out}, F_{aux})$	
9: return $s1$	

C. Model privacy evaluation

Finally, two measures of privacy named privacy scores are computed. These scores (denoted as $s1$ and $s2$) aim at evaluating the degree of privacy of segments and lightpaths models. Being applicable to either η or φ models, both scores are based on actions that can be performed by an adversary to gather information from the internals of the domain.

The first score $s1$ aims at computing the degree of similarity of each intermediate layer output with the model output. The rationale behind this approach is to find layers that become a component boundary. By definition, an intermediate layer that can potentially be a component boundary should have a shape equal to the model input and output. Note that, by merging layers between components, that true component boundary layers disappear. However, some intermediate layer of a component can have a number of neurons equal to input and output layers. Therefore, it is worth to compute this score.

Algorithm III details the computation of score $s1$, that is initialized as a vector of zeros of length equal to the number of layers of the evaluated model (lines 1-2 of Algorithm III). Then, a random set of model input values F_{in} is generated and propagated through the model to obtain the corresponding output features F_{out} (lines 3-4). This set of output features is kept as a reference and compared against the output of each partial model ending in an intermediate model layer with as many neurons as the model output size (lines 5-7). The comparison is computed in terms of the inverse of the Mean Square Error (MSE) between the reference features F_{out} and the propagated features on the partial model F_{aux} (line 8). The list of values corresponding to $s1$ is eventually returned (line 9). Note that a large value in a given position indicates that the model layer in that position is likely to be the boundary between lightpath components, due to its similarity with the expected magnitude and characteristics of a typical model output.

The second score $s2$ focuses on identifying similar patterns in groups of consecutive layers in a model, thus indicating the presence of a given component model that repeats along the path, e.g., ROADM models. Algorithm IV details the process of computing $s2$ which is initialized in the same way that $s1$ (lines 1-2 of Algorithm IV). Then, groups of c consecutive layers, where c ranges between a minimum c_{min} and a maximum c_{max} , are evaluated (line 3). For each group size c , any different pair of model weights set W_1 and W_2 is retrieved (lines 5-7), and the score based on the inverse of the MSE between W_1 and W_2 computed (line 8). Note that the obtained value is updated in the proper position of vector $s2$ if and only if it is larger than the current one (lines 9-10). In this way, the returned vector $s2$ (line 11) contains the largest similarity among all evaluated sizes and weight sets pairs, which enables finding heterogeneous similarity patterns along the lightpath model.

Algorithm IV. Score $s2$

IN: <i>model</i> (either η or φ)	OUT: $s2$
1: $n_{max} \leftarrow \text{getNumberOfLayers}(\text{model})$	
2: $s2 \leftarrow \text{zeros}(n_{max})$	
3: for c in $[c_{min}, c_{max}]$ do	
4: for i in $[2, n_{max} - c]$ do	
5: $W_1 \leftarrow \text{getWeights}(\text{model}[i..i+c])$	
6: for j in $[i+1, n_{max} - c + 1]$ do	
7: $W_2 \leftarrow \text{getWeights}(\text{model}[j..j+c])$	
8: $s \leftarrow 1/\text{MSE}(W_1, W_2)$	
9: if $s > s2[i+c]$ then	
10: $s2[i+c] \leftarrow s$	
11: return $s2$	

4. PROTECTION AGAINST MAN-IN-THE-MIDDLE ATTACKS

In this section we focus on a security use case where e2e lightpath models and other procedures and algorithms running in the OCATA NDT are used during operation. First, we present the architecture and procedure proposed to promptly detect a MitM attack performing tampering of a target lightpath by means of combining local telemetry collected in node agents and models running in the OCATA NDT at the CP site of the destination domain. Then, a more sophisticated attack strategy where tampering attack is performed in combination with evasion attacks on OC samples is presented as an evolution of MitM attack in order to remain undetectable by the proposed defense approach. Motivated by the success of this combined attack, the section ends with a novel and extended architecture that includes evasion attack detection as part of the lightpath analysis performed at the OCATA NDT, thus making the system robust against complex attacks.

A. Tampering detection

Let us consider the scenario sketched in Figure 5 where a lightpath is transparently routed from Alice to Bob (traversing one or multiple domains), being its total length equal to L km. At Bob site, the optical signal is monitored and thus, OC samples are collected, which are afterwards processed in the same local node agent. This processing consists in applying GMM to each collected OC sample X in order to obtain the set of features F . Those features are then forwarded to the telemetry manager that checks the integrity of the received features, e.g., verifying that they contain the expected number of elements and checking data types. This set of features F characterizing the last monitored OC sample is then used by a lightpath distance analysis module,

that contains a DNN model that estimates lightpath length (L') based on the dispersion of the received IQ symbols around the expected centroids [12]. Moreover, this module performs a decision-making test to determine whether $L' \cong L$ or conversely, L' is significantly different (shorter or longer) than L .

Figure 5. Detection of MitM attack performing tampering

Figure 5 considers that the lightpath is suffering a MitM attack with the malicious objective of tampering (reading and modifying) the data transported by the optical connection. Without loss of generality, we consider that Mallory has gained physical access to the intermediate site (site M), so the attacker can receive the original optical signal from Alice, alter data and forward the new signal to Bob. At this intermediate site, the optical signal has traversed L_1 km from Alice site and has to travel additional L_2 km to arrive Bob site. In addition, Mallory might need remote access to other sites along the route of the lightpath, e.g., if physical access to an intermediate site in the route of the lightpath is not possible and remote switching configuration is needed to carry out the attack. Finally, let us assume that the attack can be conducted with negligible optical transmission disruption, and therefore no loss-of-light alarm is raised.

The proposed lightpath distance analysis module can detect differences in the expected lightpath length L , which can be computed by the features estimated by the e2e lightpath model ϕ . In the example in Figure 5, the module would receive an OC sample with different properties than expected, since it has been propagated through a subset of network components, including a shorter distance. Thus, it would infer that the optical signal received by Bob has been generated by a transmitter located at $L' \cong L_2$. Therefore, a warning notification will be sent to the domain SDN controller, which eventually can trigger countermeasures and further notification to the orchestrator for multi-domain decisions.

B. Combined tampering + evasion attack

In view of the above, Mallory needs to perform additional processing to bypass the proposed security shield. In this subsection, we summarize the *Hacking Optical Constellations throUgh re-Shaping (HOCUS)* module. HOCUS performs an evasion attack by modifying I-Q symbols fingerprints so that Mallory's OC samples reaching Bob resemble the expected for the original signal [20].

Figure 6 illustrates a generic scenario where tampering and evasion is performed at the same time. For the sake of generality, let us consider that HOCUS receives source optical symbols (hereafter denoted as x_a) with total

Figure 6. Combined Tampering + Evasion Attack

accumulated length L_a and produces modified target optical symbols (x_b) with a dispersion around the OC point that resembles length L_b . With this general notation, we cover different situations, e.g., the adversary gets control of site Z and perform both tampering and evasion in the same site, or take physical control on an intermediate site M and logical control of site Z. This second case is the one illustrated in Figure 6, where $L_a = L_2$ and $L_b = L$. Note that, in the cases mentioned before, $L_a < L_b$. However, there are cases where $L_a > L_b$, e.g., if Mallory could only gain physical access to a site that is not in the original route of the lightpath. In this case, the attacker could silently reroute the lightpath so it crosses the desired intermediate site. As a consequence

of this action, L_b might be shorter than L_a .

Although HOCUS evasion could be also applied at the CP site, i.e., if OCATA NDT process is compromised, we assume that local node agents are typically more insecure and prone to have command and control vulnerabilities that can be exploited to remotely alter the normal behavior of telemetry data collection and analysis processes.

Formally, HOCUS is defined as a parametric function that requires from a set of coefficients θ to be trained before performing any re-shaping. Assuming 16QAM signals, $\theta = \{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{16}\}$, where θ_i initially contains the expected bi-variate Gaussian distribution of constellation point i for both L_a and L_b lengths.

Without loss of generality, we assume that Mallory can access monitoring data repositories, obtain true OC samples from all or part of the lightpaths in operation, and train μ and σ coefficients before performing MitM attacks. However, OCs for distances L_a and/or L_b might not be available, so polynomial interpolation is used to estimate missing coefficients from the available lightpath lengths. Note that both μ and σ coefficients present high correlation with length among all constellation points [14].

Once μ and σ for lengths L_a and L_b are obtained, transformation matrices W are computed and added to θ . Let us denote Σ as the covariance matrix formed by σ coefficients: $[[\sigma_b, \sigma_{IQ}], [\sigma_{IQ}, \sigma_Q]]$. Σ it is semi-definite positive and hence, a decomposition $\Sigma = P \cdot D \cdot P^*$ exists, being P a unitriangular matrix, D a diagonal one and P^* the conjugate transpose of P [31]. Then, transformation matrix $W_i(L_a, L_b)$ for constellation point i is computed as eq. (2):

Figure 7. Tampering + Evasion Attack Detection

$$W_i(L_a, L_b) = P_i(L_b) \cdot D_i^{\frac{1}{2}}(L_b) \cdot P_i^*(L_b) \cdot P_i(L_a) \cdot D_i^{-\frac{1}{2}}(L_a) \cdot P_i^*(L_a) \quad (2)$$

Individual symbol transformation can then be easily performed. Let us denote $x_a(t)$ as the source symbol processed by HOCUS at time t . Assuming that it belongs to constellation point i , the target symbol $x_b(t)$ is obtained by applying the transformation in eq. (3):

$$x_b(t) = W_i(L_a, L_b) \cdot (x_a(t) - \mu_i(L_a)) + \mu_i(L_b) \quad (3)$$

C. Tampering + evasion detection

The reason behind the effectiveness of HOCUS is that it applies an affine transformation of symbols in a way that the received constellation X keeps the expected features F (μ and σ) and therefore, any method based on the analysis of those features fails in detecting attacks. In this section, we extend the lightpath analysis performed at the OCATA NDT and present a novel approach to detect MitM attacks combining tampering and evasion performed by HOCUS, which is sketched in Figure 7. Thus, besides the set of features F , the node agent compresses the OC sample X by means of an AE. In particular, the encoder is placed at the node agent, in order to generate the latent space w that is then forwarded to the telemetry manager where the decoder reconstructs the original constellation X with negligible loss (we refer the reader to [8] for details about the methodology and performance evaluation of this AE-based compression of OC samples). In this way, the information exchanged between the telemetry agent and the manager remains private, since the latent space w cannot be interpreted without the required decoder.

In the OCATA NDT system, a new module is created in order to compute the difference between a received sample X and a reference one X_r , previously obtained by means of randomly sampling from e2e model ϕ . In particular, we use the Hausdorff distance [32] that gives us the greatest of all the Euclidean distances from a symbol $x \in X$ to the closest symbol $x_r \in X_r$, i.e.:

$$\text{diff}_H(X, X_r) = \max\{\sup_{x \in X} \inf_{x_r \in X_r} \|x - x_r\|_2, \sup_{x_r \in X_r} \inf_{x \in X} \|x - x_r\|_2\}, \quad (4)$$

Algorithm V. Evasion Detection

IN: $X_1, X_2, Params, Mem$	OUT: <i>attack</i>
------------------------------------	---------------------------

```

1: attack ← False
2: Mem.D.pop_first()
3: Mem.D.push(diffH( $X_1, X_2$ ))
4:  $z \leftarrow 1$ 
5: for  $d \in Mem.D$  do
6:    $z \leftarrow z \times (1 - P(d \sim N(Params.avg, Params.std)))$ 
7: if  $z > Params.\alpha$  then
8:   Mem.count ← Mem.count + 1
9:   if Mem.count = Params.β then attack ← True
10: else Mem.count ← 0
11: return attack

```

where *sup* and *inf* are the supremum and infimum, respectively. Note that, the larger the *diffH*(\cdot) metric is, the more different X and X_r are in terms of the spatial distribution of points, even when features of both OC samples are similar. Algorithm V uses of the principle of the Hausdorff distance to detect evasion attacks. This procedure is triggered periodically and it receives the new collected sample X , the reference sample X_r , a set of parameters $Params$ that includes: i) the average *avg* and standard deviation *std* of Hausdorff distance in the absence of attacks; and ii) the parameters α and β used for detection of significant differences between X and X_r ; and a memory pointer (*Mem*) that is used to store; i) D with the Hausdorff distances of the last collected samples; and ii) counter *count*. Parameters *avg* and *std* are computed by generating random samples following model ϕ , applying eq (4) to compute *diffH*(\cdot) on two samples and calculate average and standard deviation. Parameters α and β can also be tuned from the same set of random samples to avoid false attack detection.

After some initialization (line 1 in Algorithm V), set D is updated by removing the oldest value and adding the distance of the new sample (lines 2-3). Then, the indicator z is computed indicating how far the distances in D are from the expected distribution in the absence of attacks (lines 4-6). This indicator assumes that the Hausdorff distance of a given sample is an independent and identically distributed random variable following a Gaussian distribution with expectation and deviation equal to *avg* and *std*, respectively. Then, an attack is detected if and only if z exceeded α in the last β consecutive calls of the algorithm (lines 7-10). Finally, the diagnosis of attack detection at time t (True/False) is returned.

5. ILLUSTRATIVE RESULTS

In this section, we firstly introduce the simulation environment intended to reproduce the provisioning phase and posterior operation of a multi-domain lightpath. Its purpose is to numerically evaluate the privacy preserving mechanisms introduced in Section 3, as well as to reproduce tampering and evasion attacks and evaluate their detection by means of the methods presented in Section 4. Other characteristics such as secure inter-domain and intra-domain data and model sharing, e.g., encrypted communications, are assumed to be deployed in a real network and not implemented in the simulator.

A. Simulation environment

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed methodology, we implemented a Python-based simulator emulating a transparent multi-domain network according to the architecture sketched in Figure 1a. Simulation configuration includes aspects such as the number of domains and topological characteristics of each domain, as well as characteristics of the requests, such as source and destination nodes and QoT requirements. For the sake of simplicity, orchestrator and domain SDN controllers implementation have been reduced to the minimal requirements for the evaluation of the proposed algorithms and procedures. For reproducing data plane behavior and obtaining data sets for training and validation of OCATA NDT models, as well as to emulate network operation, we rely on the openly available dataset [27]. This dataset contains input and output data for training the different components including ROADMs and fiber links of different lengths. Moreover, it contains OC samples for lightpaths of distance in the range 80-2000 km, which allows emulating the operation of a large number of lightpath configurations.

The OCATA instance of each domain was loaded with component models (ROADM and fiber links ranging from 100 km to 400km) trained with data for 16- quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) OC samples available in [27]. As introduced in Section 3, each constellation point is characterized by 5 features that are propagated through the DNN models. Following the conclusions of the performance studies carried out in [12-14], and to reduce DNN models' complexity, features for only four selected constellation points ($[-3+3i]$, $[1+i]$, $[-1-i]$, and $[1-3i]$) are propagated. Then, the SNLB set contains one single DNN model per component type, with 20 input and output neurons, and 3 hidden layers with 20 tanh neurons. Regarding the ALUB set, k models per component were trained with a variable number of hidden layers (from 3 to 6), number of neurons per layer (from 10 to 30), and activation function, while ensuring the characteristics of first hidden and output layer of component models described in Section 3.

Given a multi-domain network configuration and a request, the simulator executes the workflow in Section 3.A to build the e2e model, evaluate the QoT, and establish the connection. Then, operation is simulated by selecting from the dataset in [27] the

samples that correspond to the true lightpath length and push them to the telemetry agent of the destination site. This action triggers the data pre-processing, integrity check, and analysis in order to detect the different potential attacks. This action is repeated for a number of samples in order to simulate the continuous monitoring of the e2e lightpath.

Finally, tampering is implemented by selecting the tampering site and the time instant to be produced, as well as evasion (if selected) to be performed either at the same site or destination site. This modifies the constellation sample that is received at destination node agent, in accordance with the target attack.

B. Exportable model synthesis

After presenting the simulation environment, the evaluation of the exportable model synthesis in Section 3.B is presented in this section, with special emphasis on the precision of these models with respect to benchmarking disaggregated ones. Moreover, its enhanced privacy in terms of the scores presented in Section 3.C is assessed.

Let us start analyzing the performance of some key processes of the exportable model synthesis procedure detailed in Algorithm I at Section 3.B. In particular, we focus on evaluating the diverse selection of component models to compound the exportable model ϕ , as well as evaluating the impact of truncating coefficients to increase the amount of zero weights. For this analysis, we configured lightpath segments with 1 to 4 hops, which leads to total intra-domain distances between 100 km and 1,600km.

Figure 8a shows the diversity index div as a function of the number of hops of the disaggregated model η' obtained by the model selection procedure that maximizes overall model diversity (Algorithm II). For benchmarking purposes, the figure also shows the results of randomly selecting models from ALUB database. Specifically, we built 1000 random segment models for each hop length, computed its diversity index, and summarized the results in the box plot shown in the figure. As can be observed, our procedure achieves maximum diversity for all the evaluated configurations. Note that, as soon as segment length increases, the range of diversity clearly increases, which also highlights the need of a dedicated algorithm to guarantee maximum diversity as part of the exportable model synthesis procedure.

Figure 8b illustrates the effect of truncating the weights whose absolute values are lower than truncation threshold $trunc$. For each of the segment configurations used in Figure 8a, the resultant exportable models before and after truncation are obtained, and a common set of random input values are propagated through both models. The difference within the models' output values (i.e., the additional error added by truncation) is computed in terms of MSE. The figure shows the average additional error and % of zero weights for all segment configurations as a function of $trunc$. In view of the results, we can conclude than setting up $trunc=0.1$ provides a significant percentage of zero weights (>20%) with negligible error addition.

We now focus on evaluating the performance of the whole procedure in Algorithm I. For the sake of illustrative purposes, Figure 8c shows an example of the DNN architecture of the exportable model ϕ obtained from a disaggregated model η of a lightpath with two hops of 400km each. Note that, visually, model η has an architecture that perfectly allows extracting the different components, whereas model ϕ hides the internals and boundaries of the components as expected from the different model selection and merging procedures.

Figure 8. Exportable Model Synthesis performance: diversity analysis (a); truncation threshold analysis (b); illustrative example (c)

At this point, we need to exhaustively validate the quality of the obtained exportable models with respect to the disaggregated ones. Thus, three approaches are compared: *i*) using the disaggregated model η (for benchmarking purposes), *ii*) ϕ with $k=1$ (i.e., without model diversity), and *iii*) ϕ with $k=5$ (with model diversity). In both ϕ models, $trunc$ was set to 0.1. Figure 9 compares the values of the output features after propagation for segments with different number of hops. To reduce the number of features to show, we selected features μ_l and σ_l (normalized to training values) of constellation point $[-3+3i]$ for segments with links of 100km (Figure 9a-b) and 400km (Figure 9c-d). We observe in the results that all models provide similar performance in estimating

propagated features (comparable performance is observed for the rest of propagated features). In order to better visualize the high similarity between η and φ models, Figure 10 plots the contours of bivariate Gaussian distributions characterizing constellation points $[-3+3i]$ and $[1+1i]$ for two different lightpath configurations, i.e., 4 hops of 100km each (Figure 10a-b) and 4 hops of 400km each (Figure 10c-d). In view of the figure, we clearly reinforce the message that exportable model φ allows characterizing a given lightpath with the same accuracy that its disaggregated model η does.

Figure 9. Feature propagation performance of constellation point $[-3+3i]$

Figure 10. Detail of bivariate Gaussian distribution of two different lightpath configurations

To validate the quality of the e2e φ models, we assess their accuracy for QoT estimation purposes. To this aim, we combined several segment models with different distances (emulating intra-domain segments) in an e2e lightpath model to be composed and evaluated in the destination OCATA NDT. The approach presented and validated in [13] for estimating the pre-FEC BER from propagated GMM features has been used for QoT estimation. Figure 11 shows the estimated pre-FEC BER as a function of e2e lightpath length for the considered approaches. We observe that accurate e2e QoT estimation is provided by exportable model φ ($\sim 6\%$ maximum error in the log scale with respect to benchmarking using η model).

Finally, the numerical assessment of privacy is required to confirm the goodness of the proposed exportable model synthesis approach (besides the illustrative and visual example shown in Figure 8c). Figure 12 a-b shows the score values $s1$ and $s2$, respectively, for a 4-hop lightpath segment with 400-km links, computed as detailed in Algorithm III (for $s1$) and Algorithm IV (for $s2$). Recall that $s1$ compares intermediate layer outputs with segment model output in order to find similar values, while $s2$ tries to find patterns of model coefficients that repeat along the model. For the latter, the number of consecutive layers to be analyzed to find similarity patterns ranges from $c_{min}=2$ to $c_{max}=6$. In both cases, the score is inversely proportional to MSE and large values indicate a layer that is suitable to be a component boundary (red lines show significant levels). As expected, η model provides detailed internal information; one peak per component (all ROADMs except last, and links) is clearly observed. On the contrary, components cannot be isolated by $s1$ when analyzing φ models. Moreover, adding diversity ($k=5$) prevents detecting coefficient patterns by $s2$, which validates the proposed exportable model synthesis procedure to enhance the privacy of shared models.

Figure 11. e2e QoT estimation

Figure 12. Privacy evaluation of lightpath example (4 hops of 400-km links)

C. MitM attacks detection

The impact of MitM attacks, jointly with the different countermeasures proposed in Section 4 are numerically evaluated in this section. To this aim, we assume that lightpaths are already established and thus, e2e models are available in the destination OCATA NDT and ready to be used for continuous lightpath analysis for prompt attack detection.

Let us start with the performance of the detection of tampering attack detailed in Section 4.A; in particular, we focus on the evaluation of the lightpath distance analysis module running in the OCATA NDT at the destination site. As key element in this module, the lightpath length estimator consists in a DNN-model with: *i*) 20 input neurons (5 GMM-based features of the 4 selected inner and outer constellation points); *ii*) three hidden layers with 20, 20, and 12 neurons and *tanh* activation function; and *iii*) one output neuron. Note that this estimator can be used for computing the expected length (L) obtained by providing the expected features got from the e2e lightpath model, as well as the actual length (L') obtained from the features computed by the GMM module running in the telemetry agent. Moreover, we implemented a decision-making function that detects unexpected length if the relative error between L and L' exceeds a predefined threshold thr . In order to produce accurate tampering detection, we aim at configuring a thr value so that accurate discrimination between different lengths is achieved. In the available dataset, the minimum difference between samples is 80 km, so we target such precision.

Figure 13a shows the accuracy to detect tampering attacks as a function of threshold thr . To this aim, we repeated the following procedure 10,000 times for every evaluated thr value: *i*) an expected length L in the range [80km, 2000km] is randomly selected; *ii*) a sample from the available dataset in the range [80km, 2000km] is randomly selected; *iii*) L' is computed by the lightpath length estimator model taking as input the features of the selected sample; *iv*) according to the given thr , a decision is made (either $L'=L$ or $L'\neq L$), *v*) finally, the decision is classified either as correct, false positive, or false negative according to the rules in Table 1. As can be observed in Figure 13a, configuring $thr = 0.1$ produces no false detections (neither false positives nor false negatives), which indicates 100% attack detection accuracy in the whole length range for distances as close as 80 km.

Figure 13. OC-DT training (a). Performance of HOCUS(0-> L_1) absolute (b) and normalized (c), and of HOCUS(L_2 -> L) (d).

Assuming the highly precise tampering attack detection procedure evaluated so far, now we evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed HOCUS module to perform a more sophisticated MitM attack combining tampering + evasion (Section 4.B). Firstly, we focus on evaluating HOCUS when the MitM attack is performed at the Rx site, i.e., both tampering and evasion in the same site. To this aim, we use the DNN-based lightpath length predictor to estimate $L_1 = L$. Figure 13b shows predicted vs. actual L_1 ; dotted lines represent the confidence interval assuming $thr = 0.1$. Complementing Figure 13b, Figure 13c shows the normalized prediction accuracy, where predictions within the interval [-1, 1] entail that the decision-making module cannot detect any distance inconsistency in the received signal. Owing to the fact that the attacker can use HOCUS to generate signals with similar distance than that of original signals, the MitM will be undetectable. Let us now evaluate HOCUS when applied at the Rx site but tampering is performed in another intermediate site far from the Rx site. Figure 13d presents results for actual $L = \{760, 1360, 2000\}$ km, when the tampering attack was performed at L_2 in the range [80, 1920] km from Rx. As in the previous case, the attack is not detected since the predicted L is within the accuracy interval regardless of the actual L_2 .

Figure 14 shows the detail of constellation point $(-3 + 3i)$ before (original) and after the MitM attack, without and with HOCUS. Two different cases are considered: $\langle L = 800$ km, $L_1 = 720$ km, HOCUS(0 km->720 km) \rangle (Figure 14a) and $\langle L = 1600$ km, $L_1 = 800$ km, HOCUS(800 km->1600 km) \rangle (Figure 14b). The contours of the bivariate Gaussian distributions that characterize each case are also plotted. We observe that, in both cases, HOCUS introduces additional dispersion in the symbols that results in

constellation points similar to the original ones. Table 2 details the Gaussian features for all the cases plotted in Figure 14 (values in boldface indicate a statistically significant difference with respect to the original case). It is worth noting that features related with the dispersion of symbols around their centroid are largely altered by MitM attack, whereas HOCUS performs a correction that returns dispersion close to their original state.

Figure 14. Detail of constellation point $-3 + 3i$ when HOCUS is applied at an intermediate site (a) and at the Rx site (b).

Table 1 Decision Making Evaluation

Actual	Predicted	
	$L' = L$	$L' \neq L$
$L' = L$	Correct	False Negative
$L' \neq L$	False Positive	Correct

Table 2 Detailed features of constellation point $-3 + 3i$

		μ_I	μ_Q	σ_I	σ_Q	σ_{IQ}
Int. Site (Figure 14a)	Original	-3.004	2.981	0.036	0.043	0.004
	MitM	-3.013	2.988	0.004	0.005	0.001
	MitM + HOCUS	-3.008	2.950	0.035	0.050	0.005
Rx Site (Figure 14b)	Original	-2.972	2.937	0.083	0.088	-0.007
	MitM	-3.003	2.962	0.038	0.039	0.002
	MitM + HOCUS	-2.976	2.945	0.086	0.078	-0.010

We complete the evaluation of the full detection system illustrated in Figure 7. In particular, we focus on the evaluation of evasion detection procedure detailed in Algorithm V. To this aim, we adopt the AE-based compression methodology in [8] to encode and decode samples from our available dataset, thus emulating the actual behavior of the telemetry system sketched in Figure 7. In this way, we obtain samples X' that are compared against reference samples X_r obtained by randomly sampling the features returned by the e2e lightpath model. We focus on reproducing the operation in two scenarios differing in the total lightpath distance L , as well as the distance to tampering site L_I . Figure 15a plots the evolution of indicator z for both configurations, computed at every time interval, assuming that D contains the last 5 distance measurements. A MitM attack combining tampering and evasion starts at normalized time 0. We observe that the indicator sharply increases as soon as the MitM attack starts, which allow an accurate and prompt attack detection. For short distance lightpaths, large indicator peaks are computed in the absence of attacks, which might be wrongly detected as false attacks. This is the reason behind the design of the proposed method that detects attack only when z reaches α , which is configured with a high value, e.g., 0.9, and it stays above that value for a significant amount of consecutive β samples.

Extending previous results, Figure 15b analyzes the impact of parameters α and β on the performance of evasion detection, specifically in terms of false positive detection. The curves show aggregated values for 420 different combinations of lightpaths of length L (ranging from 80 to 1600 km) and L_I (for each L , from Tx to Rx in steps of 80km). We can conclude that $\alpha=0.9$ and $\beta=3$ is the configuration that allows the fastest MitM detection with no false positives. The inset table shows that the overall accuracy achieved for the selected parametrization is larger than 98%, which definitely validates the proposed method as an effective MitM attack detection mechanism. Moreover, detection times are very short (note that it cannot be under min., as $\beta=3$) and with reduced variability among different lighthpath configurations, which demonstrate the promptness of detection.

Figure 15. Score evolution under MitM attacks (a), evasion detection performance (b)

D. Scalability considerations

Finally, let us evaluate the scalability of the main processes proposed in this paper for secure multi-domain network operation, i.e., exportable model synthesis, e2e model composition, and e2e model inference. Tests were carried out on an Intel Core i7-4790 CPU at 3.60 GHz.

Generating an exportable φ model (Algorithm I) of a domain segment similar to that represented in Figure 8c (3 ROADMs and 2 links) took less than 1s. The model has 20 fully-connected layers with a total of 320 neurons and 5,020 coefficients (weights and bias), and an overall size (configuration plus coefficients) of around 60 KB, which can be reduced to 6 KB using compression [33]. Regarding the e2e model composition at the destination site, the processing time was less than 500ms. In consequence, no remarkable scalability issues are expected from both exportable model synthesis and e2e model composition.

As for inference using the e2e model, i.e., QoT analysis and attack detection, both processes took less than 100ms to propagate inputs to outputs. So, likewise model composition, no remarkable scalability issue is expected.

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper faced the challenge of providing solutions for private and secure NDT-assisted operation of multi-domain optical networks. The main goal was to increase the security and privacy of multi-domain AN operation based on OCATA NDT entities. To this aim, an architecture and workflows were presented to allow the private exchange of ML models between domain NDTs in order to build e2e lightpath models preserving the privacy of internal domains. This mechanism allows maintaining large privacy in the ML pipeline needed to share models between domains. The proposed methods to create exportable models have been assessed and validated to generate highly private e2e lightpath models with similar accuracy to that of disaggregated ones that do not protect from internal information leakage. Thus, the secure perimeter of single-domain NDT-assisted operation can be now extended to a collaborative multi-domain scenario, which is an essential security requirement towards fully autonomous 6G networks.

The added control plane complexity by using NDT-assisted multi-domain network operation increases the attack surface and opens the possibility of performing new attacks such as the ones that affect AI/ML model operation. In particular, we demonstrate how ML pipelines allowing the detection of MitM attack can be targeted by more sophisticated attacks aiming at cancelling MitM detection. To avoid adversaries to produce undetectable, silent MitM attacks by exploiting combined threats, in this paper we presented a methodology to perform dual detection of data tampering (primary MitM objective) and model evasion (secondary attack to allow undetectable MitM). The presented methodology has been evaluated and assessed as highly accurate to perform such dual detection for a wide range of lightpath configurations. Hence, it allows concluding the need to fostering the deployment of private and secure ML pipelines to guarantee the robust and reliable NDT-assisted operation of multi-domain optical networks.

Table 3 summarizes the main threats, vulnerabilities, and countermeasures of the ecosystem presented in this paper. Those aspects that have been deeply considered by the definition of methods and algorithms and their posterior numerical evaluation are highlighted in boldface. In conclusion, securing ML pipelines of NDT-assisted multi-domain optical networks have been produced by applying countermeasures against well-known AI-based threats such as data tampering, model disclosure, and model evasion [18]. All the contributions presented in this paper aimed at contributing to the implementation of secure and trustworthy AI-based AN operation, which is one of the essential cornerstones of full AN operation (ANL5) envisioned by the end of this decade.

Table 3 Summary of threats, vulnerabilities, and countermeasures

Threat	Description	Vulnerabilities	Countermeasures
Data Disclosure	Telemetry data leakage	Lack of protection mechanisms to guarantee proper management of telemetry data during collection, pre-processing, and analysis in local agents and centralized manager	Privacy preserving data encoding Secure intra-domain data sharing
Data Tampering	Service /users data leakage/modification by MitM attacks	Lack of detection mechanisms of MitM attacks. Poor or inadequate access rights for remote command and control of software-defined control elements of domain sites.	Data tampering detection in OCATA NDT
Model Disclosure	Model (domain) internals leakage	Lack of protection mechanisms to guarantee secure and private exchange of models between domains	Privacy preserving synthesis of exportable models Secure inter-domain model sharing
Model Evasion	Evading data tampering detection to perform successful MitM attacks	Lack of methods to detect the perturbation of telemetry samples generated by an adversary with malicious purposes	Model Evasion detection in OCATA NDT

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